

Analysis of Well Water Quality Index as Panacea for Sustainable Healthy Living in Zing Local Government Area of Taraba State, Nigeria

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Abstract:

This investigation was carried out to analyze the hand-dug well water quality index as a panacea for sustainable healthy living in Zing Local Government Area of Taraba state, Nigeria. Ten (10) different hand-dug well water samples were studied for a period of six months (October- March). Various physicochemical parameters such as PH, EC, Turbidity, Total hardness, total dissolves solids, chlorides, sulphates, calcium, magnesium, total alkalinity, fluorides and phosphates were assessed using standard methods and instruments recommended by WHO. The arithmetic index method was adopted to calculate the Water Quality Index (WQI). The investigations revealed that Zing A1, Zing A2, Yakoko, Monkin A and Monkin B,

Lamma, Bitako and Bubong hand-dug well water were not suitable for domestic uses, while Zing B and Dinding showed a very poor water quality for domestic uses and human consumptions. It was therefore recommended that alternative portable sources of drinking water for these communities be provided to avert contracting waterborne diseases and that regular monitoring be encouraged by authority concerns.

Keywords: *Water Quality, Zing well water, physicochemical properties, Healthy living.*

Introduction

Information is considered as live wire of every society and how informed an individual is, is dependent on the amount and quality of information available to him. For healthy living in a society, the amount of water and its quality is sacrosanct. With the increasing rise in human population and daily demands for water

resources, the quality of the water must be assessed and evaluated.

The water quality index according to Ali (2014) depicts the composite influence of different water quality parameters and communicates water quality information to the public and legislative decision-makers. The quality of water is dependent on its purposes and applicability. The water quality index is one of the most

efficient ways or means of communicating the quality of water to the end users, regulatory bodies and policymakers. It expressed the quality in terms of how the organoleptic, physicochemical and other organic parameters are present in the water as it relates to its suitability for drinking and other domestic purposes.

According to APHA (1992), water quality indices are tools to determine conditions of water quality and like any other tool, it requires knowledge about the principles and basic concepts of water and related issues. It summarizes a large amount of water quality data into simple terms such as excellent, very good, good, poor, very poor and unsuitable. It offers an unambiguous explanation and declaration of the status of the water.

Statement of the Problem

According to World Health Organization (WHO, 2006), the healthy lifestyle of an individual's community and every society is dependent on the quality and safety of their water resources. It is estimated that 88% of most disease-causing organisms are transmitted via water and/or fluids. Water-borne diseases such as diarrhea, cholera, typhoid, giardia, dysentery, and Escherichia Coli (E. coli) are common in developing nations and are a leading cause of death in children and adults. Mottled teeth (brown teeth) are another common menace in communities with bad or unsafe water used for drinking purposes. It is against this backdrop that, it becomes expedient to evaluate and study the water quality index of Zing local government area to ascertain the status of these sources of water used for domestic purposes and household chores.

Materials and Methods

Study Area

Zing is one of the sixteen local government areas of Taraba state, northeast Nigeria lies between longitude 10° and 11°E and latitude 9° and 10°N of the equator with a land area of 1,030km² estimated population of about 170,600 (NPC

2006). It has a temperature range of 25°C to 33°C in both rainy and dry seasons with good climatic conditions for agricultural activities. The study area is endowed with a lot of natural resources such as mountains, natural grasslands, rocks, peasant and commercial farmers, shallow streams and good weather conditions for habitation. (Musa, et al., 2011).

Sample Collection

The hand dug well water samples sites/locations were purposively identified and collected from the ten (10) wards of Zing local government area of Taraba State during the months of October through December and the dry season of January through March. One (1) litre of sterile plastic bottles was systematically labelled and used in collecting the samples once every 15th day of the month. Ten (10) different well water samples for six months were collected systematically. Parameters such as Temperature, turbidity, PH, and Electrical Conductivity were determined in-situ while other chemical parameters such as nitrates, sulphates, phosphates, chlorides, magnesium, total hardness, total dissolved solids, fluorides and calcium were analyzed using the prescribed standard methods of water examination (WHO 2006).

Evaluation of the Water Quality Index

The water quality index was evaluated using the thirteen assessed physicochemical parameters essential for determining the quality of water as recommended by WHO. The Arithmetic Index method (Brown 1972 in Ali, 2014) was adopted for calculating the water quality index WQI.

$$WQI = \frac{\sum q_n W_n}{\sum W_n} \quad (1)$$

Where

WQI= water quality index,

q_n =quality rating,

W_n= unit weights.

$$Q_n = \frac{100(V_n - V_0)}{(S_n - V_0)} \quad (2)$$

Where

q_n =quality rating for the n^{th} water quality parameters.

V_n =observed value of the n^{th} parameter at a given sample point.

V_o =ideal value of an n^{th} parameter in pure water, zero (0) for all parameters except PH 7.0

S_n =Standard permissible value of the n^{th} parameters.

$$W_n = \frac{K}{S_n} \quad (3)$$

Where

W_n =unit weight for the n^{th} parameters
 S_n =Standard permissible value of the n^{th} parameters.

K = proportional constant. Is taken as 1 here which also be calculated as thus.

$$K = \frac{1}{\sum \frac{1}{S_n}} \quad (4)$$

The decisions regarding the quality of water were taken or described based on the World Health Organisation classification of water quality rating as shown in Table 1 below.

Table 1. Standard Classification of Water Quality Status

S/No.	WQI	Water status /Rating
1.	0-25	Excellent water quality
2.	26-50	Good water quality
3.	51-75	Poor water quality
4.	76-100	Very poor water quality
5.	>100	Unsuitable for drinking

Result and Discussions

The Physicochemical Properties of Well Water samples in all ten wards were assessed and the quality index (WQI) was calculated using the arithmetic Index method. The result revealed that Zing A1 and Zing A2 have an unsuitable water quality with index (WQI) of 152.7431 and 101.3609 respectively. Zing B has a value of

87.8979 which can be best described as having very poor quality because it falls within the range of 76-100. The investigation also showed that Yakoko, Monkin A and Monkin B have WQI of 128.9494, 103.3088 and 172.0015, which are all unsuitable for domestic purposes while Lamma has WQI of 294.2967, Bitako has 240.6002 and Bubong with 307.4463 WQI which are by far beyond the 100 WQI, it can therefore be said that these sources of well water are unsuitable for human consumption and other domestic chores. Dinding ward showed a WQI of 95.1652 which is within the range of very poor quality for human consumption and household uses (Tab 1&2).

Conclusions

Generally, based on the findings of these investigations, it is concluded that the sampled hand-dug well water in Zing is unsuitable for domestic use. It is therefore recommended that alternative safer sources of water be provided by both private individuals and the government to safeguard the healthy living of the populace. It is also recommended that there should be regular monitoring of these sources of Water by assessing their physicochemical properties and organoleptic properties to keep them within the safe limits as approved by the world health organization and Nigerian Standard for Water Quality.

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Appendix 1

Table 2. Summary of Zing Water Quality Status

S/No.	Ward	WQI	Comments /Remarks
1.	Zing A1.	152.7431	>100, unsuitable
2.	Zing A2	101.3609	>100, unsuitable
3.	Zing B	87.8979	>75 and <100, very poor water quality.
4.	Yakoko	128.9494	>100, unsuitable
5.	Monkin A	103.3088	>100, unsuitable
6.	Monkin B	172.0015	>100, unsuitable
7.	Lamma	294.2967	>100, unsuitable
8.	Bitako	240.6002	>100, unsuitable
9.	Bubong	307.4463	>100, unsuitable
10.	Dinding	95.1652	>75 and < 100, very poor water quality.

Table 3. Zing A1 Water quality index (WQI)

Parameters	Observed value (V_n)	Standard Acceptable value (S_n).	Unit weight (W_n)	Quality rating (q_n)	$q_n W_n$
PH	7.10	6.5-8.5	0.1176	6.6667	0.7840
EC ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)	820	1000	0.001	82	0.082
Turb. (NTU)	5.23	5	0.20	104.60	20.92
T.A (mg/L)	196.67	150	0.0067	131.1113	0.8785
T.H (mg/L)	239.67	500	0.002	47.934	0.0959
TDS (mg/L)	397.50	500	0.002	79.50	0.1590
Cl^- (mg/L)	1.53	250	0.004	0.612	0.0025
SO_4^{2-} (mg/L)	51.50	250	0.004	20.60	0.0824
PO_4^{2-} (mg/L)	5.87	6.50	0.1538	90.3077	13.8893
F^- (mg/L)	3.18	1.50	0.6667	212	141.3404
Ca (mg/L)	12.56	75	0.0133	16.7467	0.2227
Mg (mg/L)	10.91	30	0.0333	36.3667	1.2110
NO_3^- (mg/L)	16.85	50	0.02	33.7	0.674
			$\Sigma W_n=1.2204$	$\Sigma q_n=1165.4451$	$\Sigma q_n W_n=180.3417$
Zing A ₁ water quality Index $WQI = \Sigma q_n W_n / \Sigma W_n = 180.3417 / 1.2204 = 147.77$					

Table 4. Zing A2 Water quality index (WQI)

Parameters	Observed value (V_n)	Standard Acceptable value (S_n).	Unit weight (W_n)	Quality rating (q_n)	$q_n W_n$
PH	7.01	6.5-8.5	0.1176	0.6667	0.0784
EC ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)	358	1000	0.001	35.80	0.0358
Turb.(NTU)	13.52	5	0.20	270.40	54.08
T.A (mg/L)	246.67	150	0.0067	164.4467	1.1018
T.H (mg/L)	202	500	0.002	40.40	0.0808
TDS (mg/L)	183.17	500	0.002	36.6340	0.0733
Cl^- (mg/L)	0.53	250	0.004	0.2120	8.48×10^{-4}
SO_4^{2-} (mg/L)	14	250	0.004	5.60	0.0224
PO_4^{2-} (mg/L)	12.42	6.50	0.1538	191.0769	29.3876
F^- (mg/L)	0.83	1.50	0.6667	55.3333	36.8907
Ca (mg/L)	1.82	75	0.0133	2.4267	0.0323
Mg (mg/L)	13.93	30	0.0333	46.4333	1.5462

NO ₃ ⁻ (mg/L)	9.28	50	0.02	18.56	0.3712
			ΣW _n =1.2204	Σq _n =867.9896	Σq _n W _n =123.7009
Zing A ₂ water quality Index WQI= Σq _n W _n / ΣW _n =123.7009/1.2204=101.3609					

Table 5. Zing B Water quality index (WQI)

Parameters	Observed value (V _n)	Standard Acceptable value (S _n).	Unit weight (W _n)	Quality rating (q _n)	q _n W _n
PH	7.08	6.5-8.5	0.1176	5.3333	0.6272
EC (μS/cm)	663.67	1000	0.001	66.367	0.0664
Turb.(NTU)	7.50	5	0.20	150	30
T.A (mg/L)	200	150	0.0067	133.3333	0.8933
T.H (mg/L)	286	500	0.002	57.20	0.1140
TDS (mg/L)	308.50	500	0.002	61.70	0.1234
Cl ⁻ (mg/L)	0.83	250	0.004	0.332	1.328×10 ⁻⁴
SO ₄ ²⁻ (mg/L)	43	250	0.004	17.20	0.0688
PO ₄ ²⁻ (mg/L)	1.65	6.50	0.1538	25.3846	3.9042
F ⁻ (mg/L)	1.57	1.50	0.6667	104.6667	69.7813
Ca (mg/L)	14.49	75	0.0133	19.32	0.2569
Mg (mg/L)	9.75	30	0.0333	32.50	1.0823
NO ₃ ⁻ (mg/L)	8.82	50	0.02	17.64	0.3528
			ΣW _n =1.2204	Σq _n =690.9769	Σq _n W _n =107.2707
Zing B\ water quality Index WQI= Σq _n W _n / ΣW _n = 107.2707/1.2204=87.8979					

Table 6. Yakoko Water quality index (WQI)

Parameters	Observed value (V _n)	Standard Acceptable value (S _n).	Unit weight (W _n)	Quality rating (q _n)	q _n W _n
PH	6.72	6.5-8.5	0.1176	33.3333	3.9199
EC (μS/cm)	905.67	1000	0.001	90.567	0.0906
Turb.(NTU)	2.07	5	0.20	41.40	0.28
T.A (mg/L)	204.17	150	0.0067	136.1133	0.9119
T.H (mg/L)	334	500	0.002	66.80	0.1336
TDS (mg/L)	457	500	0.002	91.40	0.1828
Cl ⁻ (mg/L)	0.60	250	0.004	0.24	9.6×10 ⁻⁴
SO ₄ ²⁻ (mg/L)	57.17	250	0.004	22.868	0.0915
PO ₄ ²⁻ (mg/L)	1.86	6.50	0.1538	28.6154	4.3953
F ⁻ (mg/L)	3.28	1.50	0.6667	218.6667	145.7851
Ca (mg/L)	16.23	75	0.0133	21.64	0.2878
Mg (mg/L)	10.54	30	0.0333	35	1.1655
NO ₃ ⁻ (mg/L)	3.12	50	0.02	6.24	0.1248
			ΣW _n =1.2204	Σq _n =792.884	Σq _n W _n =157.3698
Yakoko water quality Index WQI= Σq _n W _n / ΣW _n =157.3698/1.2204= 128.9494					

Table 7. Monkin A- Water quality index (WQI)

Parameters	Observed value (V _n)	Standard Acceptable value (S _n).	Unit weight (W _n)	Quality rating (q _n)	q _n W _n
PH	7.10	6.5-8.5	0.1176	6.6667	0.7840
EC (μS/cm)	217	1000	0.001	21.7	0.0217
Turb.(NTU)	0.69	5	0.20	13.8	2.76
T.A (mg/L)	165	150	0.0067	110	0.737

T.H (mg/L)	99.17	500	0.002	19.834	0.0397
TDS (mg/L)	105.5	500	0.002	21.1	0.0422
Cl ⁻ (mg/L)	0.67	250	0.004	0.268	1.072×10 ⁻³
SO ₄ ²⁻ (mg/L)	18.67	250	0.004	7.468	0.0299
PO ₄ ²⁻ (mg/L)	10.69	6.50	0.1538	164.4615	25.2942
F ⁻ (mg/L)	2.12	1.50	0.6667	141.3333	94.2267
Ca (mg/L)	3.17	75	0.0133	4.2267	0.0562
Mg (mg/L)	15.22	30	0.0333	50.7333	1.6894
NO ₃ ⁻ (mg/L)	9.90	50	0.02	19.80	0.396
			ΣW _n =1.2204	Σq _n =580.3915	Σq _n W _n =126.0781
Monkin A- water quality Index WQI= Σq _n W _n / ΣW _n = 126.0781/1.2204=103.3088					

Table 8. Monkin B - Water quality index (WQI)

Parameters	Observed value (V _n)	Standard Acceptable value (S _n).	Unit weight (W _n)	Quality rating (q _n)	q _n W _n
PH	7.40	6.5-8.5	0.1176	26.6667	3.1360
EC (μS/cm)	78.66	1000	0.001	7.866	0.007866
Turb. (NTU)	34.59	5	0.20	691.8	138.36
T.A (mg/L)	118.33	150	0.0067	78.8867	0.5285
T.H (mg/L)	100.83	500	0.002	20.166	0.0403
TDS (mg/L)	93.83	500	0.002	18.766	0.0375
Cl ⁻ (mg/L)	0.69	250	0.004	0.276	0.000552
SO ₄ ²⁻ (mg/L)	14.0	250	0.004	5.6	0.0112
PO ₄ ²⁻ (mg/L)	9.27	6.50	0.1538	142.6154	21.9343
F ⁻ (mg/L)	1.0	1.50	0.6667	66.6667	44.4467
Ca (mg/L)	3.40	75	0.0133	4.5333	0.0603
Mg (mg/L)	8.60	30	0.0333	28.6667	0.9546
NO ₃ ⁻ (mg/L)	9.82	50	0.02	19.64	0.3928
			ΣW _n =1.2204	Σq _n =1112.1495	Σq _n W _n =209.911
Monkin B- water quality Index WQI= Σq _n W _n / ΣW _n =209.9106/1.2204=172.0015					

Table 9. Lamma Water quality index (WQI)

Parameters	Observed value (V _n)	Standard Acceptable value (S _n).	Unit weight (W _n)	Quality rating (q _n)	q _n W _n
PH	6.58	6.5-8.5	0.1176	28	3.2928
EC (μS/cm)	136	1000	0.001	13.6	0.0136
Turb.(NTU)	53.74	5	0.20	1074.8	214.96
T.A (mg/L)	87.50	150	0.0067	58.3333	0.3908
T.H (mg/L)	54.67	500	0.002	10.934	0.0219
TDS (mg/L)	65	500	0.002	13	0.026
Cl ⁻ (mg/L)	4.70	250	0.004	1.88	7.52×10 ⁻³
SO ₄ ²⁻ (mg/L)	35.67	250	0.004	14.268	0.0571
PO ₄ ²⁻ (mg/L)	13.37	6.50	0.1538	205.6923	31.6355
F ⁻ (mg/L)	2.38	1.50	0.6667	158.6667	105.7831
Ca (mg/L)	5.42	75	0.0133	7.2267	0.0961
Mg (mg/L)	13.37	30	0.0333	44.5667	1.4841
NO ₃ ⁻ (mg/L)	34.78	50	0.02	69.56	1.3912
			ΣW _n =1.2204	Σq _n =1700.5277	Σq _n W _n =359.159
Lamma water quality Index WQI= Σq _n W _n / ΣW _n = 359.1597/1.2204=294.2967					

Table 10. Bitako Water quality index (WQI)

Parameters	Observed value (V_n)	Standard Acceptable value (S_n).	Unit weight (W_n)	Quality rating (q_n)	$q_n W_n$
PH	7.54	6.5-8.5	0.1176	36	4.2336
EC ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)	351.67	1000	0.001	35.167	0.0352
Turb.(NTU)	7.83	5	0.20	156.6	31.32
T.A (mg/L)	170	150	0.0067	113.3333	0.7593
T.H (mg/L)	122	500	0.002	24.40	0.0488
TDS (mg/L)	180	500	0.002	36	0.072
Cl^- (mg/L)	2.07	250	0.004	0.828	3.312×10^{-3}
SO_4^{2-} (mg/L)	13.3	250	0.004	5.32	0.0213
PO_4^{2-} (mg/L)	10.86	6.50	0.1538	167.0769	25.6964
F^- (mg/L)	5.18	1.50	0.6667	345.3333	230.2337
Ca (mg/L)	5.78	75	0.0133	7.7067	0.1025
Mg (mg/L)	8.22	30	0.0333	27.40	0.9124
NO_3^- (mg/L)	4.75	50	0.02	9.50	0.19
			$\Sigma W_n=1.2204$	$\Sigma q_n=964.6652$	$\Sigma q_n W_n=293.6285$
Bitako water quality Index $WQI = \Sigma q_n W_n / \Sigma W_n = 293.6285 / 1.2204 = 240.6002$					

Table 11. Bubong Water quality index (WQI)

Parameters	Observed value (V_n)	Standard Acceptable value (S_n).	Unit weight (W_n)	Quality rating (q_n)	$q_n W_n$
PH	7.79	6.5-8.5	0.1176	52.6667	6.1936
EC ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)	376.67	1000	0.001	37.667	0.0377
Turb.(NTU)	12.58	5	0.20	251.6	50.32
T.A (mg/L)	224.17	150	0.0067	149.4467	1.0013
T.H (mg/L)	143.33	500	0.002	28.666	0.0573
TDS (mg/L)	190.50	500	0.002	38.1	0.0762
Cl^- (mg/L)	1.32	250	0.004	0.528	2.112×10^{-3}
SO_4^{2-} (mg/L)	13.05	250	0.004	5.22	0.0209
PO_4^{2-} (mg/L)	6.99	6.50	0.1538	107.5385	16.5394
F^- (mg/L)	6.50	1.50	0.6667	433.3333	288.9033
Ca (mg/L)	8.18	75	0.0133	10.9067	0.1451
Mg (mg/L)	15.77	30	0.0333	52.5667	1.7505
NO_3^- (mg/L)	5.08	50	0.02	0.02	10.16
			$\Sigma W_n=1.2204$	$\Sigma q_n=1168.7596$	$\Sigma q_n W_n=375.2074$
Bubong water quality Index $WQI = \Sigma q_n W_n / \Sigma W_n = 375.2074 / 1.2204 = 307.4463$					

Table 12. Drinking Water quality index (WQI)

Parameters	Observed value (V_n)	Standard Acceptable value (S_n).	Unit weight (W_n)	Quality rating (q_n)	$q_n W_n$
PH	7.37	6.5-8.5	0.1176	24.6667	2.9008
EC ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)	323	1000	0.001	32.3	0.0323
Turb. (NTU)	7.87	5	0.20	157.4	31.48
T.A (mg/L)	215	150	0.0067	1.4333	9.603×10^{-3}
T.H (mg/L)	141	500	0.002	28.2	0.0564
TDS (mg/L)	162.33	500	0.002	32.466	0.0649
Cl^- (mg/L)	0.34	250	0.004	0.136	5.44×10^{-4}
SO_4^{2-} (mg/L)	16	250	0.004	64	0.256
PO_4^{2-} (mg/L)	11.83	6.50	0.1538	182	27.9916

F ⁻ (mg/L)	1.17	1.50	0.6667	78	52.0026
Ca (mg/L)	4.43	75	0.0133	5.9067	0.0786
Mg (mg/L)	9.31	30	0.0333	31.0333	1.0334
NO ₃ ⁻ (mg/L)	5.82	50	0.02	11.64	0.2328
			$\Sigma W_n=1.2204$	$\Sigma q_n=649.182$	$\Sigma q_n W_n=116.1396$
Dinding water quality Index $WQI = \Sigma q_n W_n / \Sigma W_n = 116.1396 / 1.2204 = 95.1652$					